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Spatiotemporal Dynamics of *Plasmodium falcifarum* Malaria in Gwarzo LGA, Kano State, Nigeria

Asmau Hamza Abubakar and Sani Tajo Tukur

Department of Science Laboratory Technology,
Federal Polytechnic Kobo, Kano, Nigeria

ABSTRACT

Despite substantial malaria control efforts in Nigeria, the burden remains high in several rural areas. This highlights the need for interventions that are tailored to local ecological settings. A cross-sectional study was conducted between November 2024 and August 2025 to assess malaria transmission dynamics in irrigation settlements of Gwarzo LGA, Kano State. Epidemiological and entomological indices were integrated across five communities: Unguwar Tudu, Lakwaya, Mainika, Kutama, and Kara.

Malaria prevalence varied across the settlements, with Unguwar Tudu recording the highest prevalence (18.0%), followed by Kara (17.8%), Lakwaya (14.0%), Kutama (13.7%), and Mainika (11.0%). A strong positive correlation was observed between mosquito density and malaria prevalence. *Anopheles gambiae* was the predominant vector species. Spatial clustering of malaria cases was observed across households near irrigation sites. Malaria transmission in the study area is strongly influenced by irrigation ecology, driving vector abundance and heterogeneous risk. Control strategies in rural settings should therefore integrate ecological risk mapping with targeted vector control.

Keywords: Malaria transmission; *Anopheles gambiae*; irrigation ecology; spatial clustering; vector abundance; Kano State; Nigeria.

INTRODUCTION

Despite the significant effort driven by local and international funding agencies such as regional malaria control programmes and the World Health Organisation (WHO), malaria burden has, however, remained high. This is statistically clear as some African countries show a trend of increasing malaria incidence over the past few years (Monroe *et al.*, 2022). Twenty-nine countries accounted for 95% of malaria cases globally, the breakdown of which is: Nigeria (27%), the Democratic Republic of the Congo (12%), Uganda (5%) and Mozambique (4%) accounted for almost half of all the cases globally (WHO, 2022). This increase in the number of malaria cases coincides with a weakening of the surveillance and monitoring of disease trend (WHO, 2023) which strongly underscores the need for evidence-based strategic planning and innovations tailored to the evolving dynamics of malaria transmission.

A wide range of metrics exists for monitoring malaria parasite transmission of which the strengths and limitations of each metric are related to the step of the parasite transmission cycle it measures (Tusting *et al.*, 2014). Two of the most commonly monitored metrics are the prevalence of Plasmodium parasites or parasite rate (PR) in humans and the entomological inoculation rate (EIR) (Amoah *et al.*, 2021). The prevalence of *Plasmodium* parasites in human population at a given time point (i.e., PR) approximates the reservoir of hosts potentially available to transmit the parasite from humans to mosquitoes (Feufack-Donfack *et al.*, 2021). The EIR provides an estimate of the intensity of parasite transmission from mosquitoes to humans expressed as the number of infectious bites received per person per unit time (Kilama *et al.*, 2014). These metrics are indicative of components that provide useful information about

the underlying risk of malaria parasite transmission (Amoah *et al.*, 2021). The joint monitoring of these two indices of malaria transmission in space and time allows identification and evaluation of the spatial heterogeneities and temporal patterns of transmission at fine resolution so as to potentially identify hotspot for targeted intervention (Amoah *et al.*, 2021; Feufack-Donfack *et al.*, 2021).

Several studies in Nigeria have combined epidemiological and entomological indices to better understand malaria transmission dynamics. One of the most earliest and comprehensive was the famous Garki Project conducted in northern Nigeria in Kano and Jigawa States. This study provided foundational evidence of the interaction between epidemiological and entomological factors under intervention scenarios. Longitudinal data revealed that high EIRs persisted despite mass drug administration and indoor residual spraying, highlighting the resilience of malaria transmission in Sudan–Savanna ecologies (Molineaux & Gramiccia, 1980). Several other researches includes that of Ebenezer *et al.* (2016) in Bayelsa State, where hospital incidence data and parasite prevalence were integrated with entomological inoculation rates (EIR) across multiple eco-zones. The study demonstrated a strong quantitative link between EIR and both malaria incidence and prevalence, with *Anopheles gambiae s.s.* identified as the most efficient vector (Ebenezer, Noutcha, and Okiwelu, 2016). This provides a methodological precedent for linking mosquito indices to human infection outcomes. While Odoula *et al.* (2016) highlighted the role of rainfall and seasonality in shaping vector density and malaria incidence, emphasizing the importance of aligning entomological surveillance with epidemiological monitoring to capture temporal shifts in transmission. Recently an entomological surveillance conducted in north-western Nigeria has confirmed ongoing transmission potential and widespread insecticide resistance among *Anopheles gambiae* complex populations. Although primarily vector-focused, these studies provide critical context for interpreting epidemiological data in contemporary rural settings (Ibrahim, Wondji, and Riveron, 2023).

These studies collectively demonstrate the impact of combining human and vector data to offer a more complete picture of malaria transmission heterogeneity across Nigeria. Moreover, they highlight key drivers relevant to irrigation settlements including seasonality, species composition, sporozoite infectivity, and ecological proximity to breeding sites which are essential for designing locally adapted control strategies.

Gwarzo LGA has been known for irrigation farming of number crops. The construction of irrigation system networks the LGA. These extensive irrigational channel networks provide an abundant mosquito breeding sites throughout the year, hence changing the malaria situation. There is lack of information the risk of malaria transmission to vector status in the LGA.

METHODOLOGY

Study Area

The study was conducted in Gwarzo LGA, Kano State. It has an area of approx. 393km² and a population of 183,987 (2006 census). It is well known for various agricultural activities which has being the primary occupation for the majority of its population. The population is semi urban and some part of rural. It is famous for irrigation farming of number of crops and vegetables and also thriving livestock rearing of cattle, sheep, and goats among others. The agriculture, which is the major economic activity, is dominated by both rain fed and irrigation (dry seasons).

Ethical Approval

Permission for the entomological and parasitological studies was obtained from the Human Ethical Committee of the State Ministry of Health.

The village heads and district heads were informed prior to commencement of the study. Household owners signed informed consent for mosquito collection and blood sample collection.

Mosquito Sample Collection

Adult mosquitoes were collected monthly for a period of twelve (10) months. Mosquitoes were collected inside rooms by Pyrethrum Spray Collection (PSC), with the help of trained house wives. The mosquitoes were collected from the rooms in which people slept the previous night. The PSC was carried out monthly between 4.30am – 6.30am on the day of the collection. Food, cooking utensils, animal pets were removed from the room. A white sheet of cloth about 2x4m was used to cover the entire surface of the floor. Doors

and windows were closed and the room sprayed with aerosol containing non-residual pyrethrum insecticide for 2 minutes. Knocked down mosquitoes were picked carefully with entomological forceps. Mosquitoes were transferred to petri-dish, labeled and transported to entomology laboratory at center for infectious disease research (CIDR), Aminu Kano Teaching Hospital (Epopa *et al.*, 2019).

Mosquito Species Identification

Mosquitoes collected were sorted and identified taxonomically to species level. Identification of *Anopheles* was based on morphological criteria according to established taxonomic keys (Gillies and Coetzee, 1987). Female *Anopheles* were examined under a dissecting microscope and classified on the basis of their abdominal condition as unfed, freshly fed, half-gravid and gravid (WHO, 2003).

Molecular Identification

Identification of members of *An. gambiae* complex was carried out using PCR assay. DNA extraction was carried out using Livak extraction buffer. The PCR was performed using primers designed by Scott *et al.* (1993) for identification of members of *Anopheles gambiae* sl, including universal primer (UN) (GTG TGC CCC TTC CTC GAT GT) *An gambiae* primer (GA) (CTG GTT TGG TCG GCA CGT TT) (390bp), *An arabiensis* primer (AR) (AAG TGT CCT TCT CCA TCC TA) (315bp). The reaction mixture were prepared by adding 1µl of the DNA template , 12.5µl mastermix (QDSBio Dongsheng biotech), 6.5µl nuclease free water and 1µl of each of the set of primers. The PCR condition were set on Master cyclerX50s machine and the conditions were set as follows. Initial denaturation 94°C at 3min followed by 35 cycles of denaturation 94°C at 30mins, annealing 60°C at 30mins and extension 72°C at 3mins, then final extension 72°C at 3mins. The PCR products were run 2.5% agarose gel for 60mins at 100V. The result was viewed under ultra violet light.

Female Anopheles Mosquito CSPs Detection

The heads and thoraces of identified female *Anopheles* were used to detect ciccumsporozoite antigen (CSP) of *P. falciparum* malaria using Enzyme-Linked Immuno-Sorbent Assay (ELISA). Heads and thoraces were grinded in 50 µl blocking buffer (BB) to form mosquito homogenate. Laboratory-colony of *Anopheles* was used as negative controls. The ELISA was carried out according to MR4 protocol. The optical density was determined at 414 nm in the microplate ELISA reader. Samples with green color and with optical density values of greater than two times the average optical density of the negative controls were considered sporozoite positive.

Calculation of Entomological Indices

Human-biting rate, sporozoite rate and entomological inoculation rate were calculated according to WHO (2003) guidelines, as follows:

$$\text{HBR} = \frac{\text{No. of Anopheles spp caught}}{\text{No. of occupants in rooms sampled}}$$

$$\text{SR} = \frac{\text{No. of Anopheles spp infected}}{\text{Total No. of Anopheles spp examined}}$$

$$\text{EIR} = \text{SR} \times \text{HBR}$$

Where HBR= Human bite rate, SR = sporozoite rate, EIR =entomological inoculation rate

Estimation of Parasite Rate

In the estimation of parasite rate, cross-sectional survey was conducted in a total of 200 Households selected from five wards based on their proximity to irrigation areas including, Mai nika, Kara, Kutama, Lakwaya and Unguwar Tudu.

During the sample collection, information on age, fever, ITN usage and recent anti-malarial used were collected using study questionnaire. Recent anti-malarial (AM) use as receiving antimalarial in any dosage at any time within the 2 weeks prior to the survey. During the survey, finger prick blood sample was collected from study participants to determine parasite rate using *Plasmodium falcifarum* HRP rapid diagnostic kit (RDT).

RESULTS

Table 1: Seasonal Distribution of Malaria Vectors

MONTHS	UNGUWAR TUDU		KARA		LAKWAYA		KUTAMA		MAINIKA	
	AG	AA	AG	AA	AG	AA	AG	AA	AG	AA
Nov	5	2	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
Dec	2	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Jan	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Feb	5	1	2	1	2	0	1	0	0	0
Mar	25	1	23	0	12	0	9	0	7	0
Apr	35	2	26	0	15	0	8	0	9	0
May	37	1	29	0	13	0	12	0	19	0
Jun	45	5	19	1	12	3	15	0	28	0
Jul	51	3	52	3	37	1	28	3	37	1
Aug	61	2	45	2	39	0	39	0	38	2

AG-*An. gambiae*, AA-*An. arabiensis*

Fig 1: Abundance of *An. gambiae* and *arabiensis*, U/Tudu

Fig 2: Abundance of *An. gambiae* and *arabiensis*, Kutama

Fig 3: Abundance of *An. gambiae* and *arabiensis*, Lakwaya

Fig 4: Abundance of *An. gambiae* and *arabiensis*, Kara

Fig 4: Abundance of *An. gambiae* and *arabiensis*, Mainika

Table 2: Entomological Indices of Malaria vectors across Study Area

Communities	HBR	SPR	EIR
Unguwar Tudu		12	6.25
Kara		7.3	5.35
Lakwaya		3.9	8.49
Kutama		3.3	7.52
Mai Nika		3.3	5

HBR-Human Biting Rate, SPR-Sporozoite Rate, EIR-Entomological Inoculation Rate

Table 3: Malaria Prevalence across the Study Area. A total of 987 volunteers were recruited from 200 households for the cross sectional survey of malaria prevalence in the study area. About 39% of volunteers were recruited from Unguwar Tudu, 27% from Kara, 12% from Lakwaya, 13% from Kutama and 9% from Mai nika communities to determine *Plasmodium falcifarum* malaria prevalence.

Table 3: *Plasmodium falcifarum* Parasite Rate (PR) across Communities

Communities	Residents	Prevalence (%)
Unguwar Tudu	75	18
Kara	39	17.8
Lakwaya	33	14
Kutama	24	13.7
Mai Nika	16.6	11

Table 4: Entomological and Parasitological Indices of Malaria Transmission

Communities	EIR	PR
Unguwar Tudu	384	18
Kara	266	17.8
Lakwaya	118	14
Kutama	128	13.7
Mai Nika	88	11

NB EIR-Entomological Inoculation Rate, PR-Parasite rate

DISCUSSIONS

This study highlights the integration of entomological and parasitological indices of malaria to better understand pattern of malaria transmission in rural communities. This integrated approach reveals transmission risk in communities living within the vicinity of irrigation sites. Although all the selected communities were rural irrigated, they showed significant difference in terms of agricultural activities and hence differs in the abundance and density of malaria vector spp. This highlights the need to integrate ecological characteristics relevant to a community to accurately design malaria control programs.

Despite the contribution of agricultural development in offering clear economic benefits to local communities (Zhou *et al.*, 2022) the irrigation induced activities can affect the environment and lead to enhanced malaria transmission. This in turn, may compromise the effectiveness of elimination efforts. In this study, we conducted cross-sectional epidemiologic survey of *Plasmodium falcifarum* malaria parasite together with longitudinal survey of malaria vectors. We found higher number of malaria vectors in communities where irrigation is more intense. Although there was season fluctuation in the abundance of malaria vectors, as the density of the vectors is more pronounced during the rainy than the dry months. The presence of malaria vectors throughout the collection period indicates the contribution of irrigation activities in maintaining transmission gaps during the dry months.

In addition, cross sectional survey conducted on parasite prevalence reveal higher parasite rate in communities where more irrigation activities are conducted than others. This provides direct relationship between mosquito density and malaria prevalence. The PR was consistently higher in the communities where there was higher density of malaria vectors. It is interesting to note that we observed direct pattern in *Plasmodium falcifarum* malaria transmission with respect to residents of five communities in the study setting likely due to similar malaria vectors responsible for the transmission. These results highlight the importance of longitudinal surveillance, across different transmission season.

Previous studies conducted in Nigeria reveal malaria transmission hot spots, which are located in rural areas although most are vector specific (Abubakar *et al.*, 2024; Amaechi *et al.*, 2018; Okorie *et al.*, 2011). This household surveillance study confirmed communities with high EIR, are the same experiencing higher PR. The impact of this irrigation in malaria transmission is evidence significantly contributed to the malaria persistence across the Northern part of the country with the growing expansion of agricultural activities.

This surveillance provided important longitudinal information on the patterns of malaria vectors in irrigated ecological setting. Clinical malaria cases reported at health facilities have been used for intervention evaluation but these study detected the true malaria situation, by providing direct evidence of the impact of irrigation on malaria transmission through surveillance of households in remote areas located near major breeding sites. As the government is providing investments in agricultural development to combat food insecurity and to accommodate rapid population growth. It is as well important to modify new and enhanced vector control measures to complement core vector control interventions and to reinvigorate progress towards malaria elimination.

These results demonstrate that irrigation activities likely compromised the effectiveness of the enhanced vector intervention in the study area due to persistent malaria vectors.

CONCLUSIONS

Malaria transmission in Gwarzo LGA is intense due to high EIR and PR recorded high density of malaria vectors were observed during which corresponds to high prevalence rate in areas where irrigation is high. As matter of fact, governments are providing investment in agricultural development to combat food insecurity and to accommodate rapid population growth. It is as well important to modify new and enhanced vector control measures to complement core vector control interventions and to reinvigorate progress towards malaria elimination.

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